

***Sterculia urens* Roxb. a Promising Gum Secreting Tree Used in Worldwide Food Industries**

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Abstract:

Considerable value of gum has increased in food industry, and is essentially prime constituent in liquid and semi-solid food. *Sterculia urens* Roxb. is a deciduous tree species and is native to India. It is known for its gum exudates called as Gum Karaya which is having worldwide importance in the food industries. Gum Karaya plays important role in food, baking, and dairy industries. The unique features of gum such as high water retention capacity, high viscosity, inherent, intrinsic nature, and ample availability are the main reasons for its wide usage. Karaya gum extends the shelf life of bakery foodstuffs and also decelerates aging of the food material by improving tolerance to variations in water addition and mixing. It is used in manufacturing ice pops, sherbets, French dressing, cheese spreads, meringue, meat products etc.

In addition, Gum Karaya is widely used in pharmaceuticals also and large part of gum is used as a bulk laxative. Moreover due to safe applicability and its physicochemical properties, promising role has been observed in drug delivery system, bioremediation, paper & textiles etc. various karaya gum products available in the market are widely used in food industry, suspension & gel formation, peristomal skin protection, treatment of intestinal disorders like constipation, diarrhea, and bloating, etc. *Sterculia urens* has embraced significant values in international trade market due to its exceptional properties. According to the current market reports, the global market share for karaya gum powder form is recorded to be 93.10% with an annual growth rate of 3.4% for a period of 2017–2025. Excessive consumption of karaya gum has resulted in critically low abundance and thus this plant is now considered as endangered plant species in some states of India. Keeping in view its endangered status, conservation, and mass scale production through micropropagation are fruitful towards maintaining its biological abundance.

Keywords:

Gum Karaya, food industries, pharmaceuticles, endangered status, micropropagation.

Biography:

Dr. M.M.Sharma, Associate Professor and Former Head, Department of Biosciences, Manipal University Jaipur having specialization in plant tissue culture and study on symbiotic association of fungal endophytes within plant tissues. I have published about more than 40 research papers in National & International journals of repute. Two Ph.Ds awarded and three research scholars are currently pursuing their Doctoral studies under my supervision. Besides, three externally funded research projects from National Medicinal Plants Board, University Grants Commission, New Delhi, Government of India and Rajasthan State Department of Science & Technology sanctioned to me, out of which UGC project has already completed successfully and two projects are currently under process.

Characterization of Rv1900c of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* and deciphering its role in intracellular survival

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Abstract:

Mycobacterium tuberculosis is the most successful pathogen that the mankind has come across. Global TB Report 2018 revealed that India has highest number (27%) of TB cases in the world. The bacterium can persist inside the body for decades in dormant stage. Stored triacylglycerol (TAG) is one of the major factors that are known to play role during this stage. Around, 4000 gene products were annotated in the genome of *M. tuberculosis* and 26 (LipA- lipZ) of them are annotated as putative lipases/esterases. Rv1900c of *M. tuberculosis* Lip family annotated as LipJ; conserved in all mycobacterium species contains two domains, α/β hydrolase domain at its N- terminal and C- terminal cyclase homology domain. In this report, Rv1900c and N-terminal was cloned and expressed in pET28a/*E. coli* BL21 expression system. Thereafter, both proteins were purified to homogeneity and were characterized biophysically by using CD spectrophotometry. To demonstrate the role of proteins in intracellular survival, both genes were cloned and expressed in pVV16/*Mycobacterium smegmatis* mc2155 system. The results showed significant increase in the survival of rv1900c and N-terminal as compared to pVV16 at 24, 48 and 72 hours. *M. smegmatis* expressing rv1900c and N-terminal had considerable survival under low pH, lysozyme, SDS and under nutrient stress conditions as compared to control. Our study demonstrated an important role of Rv1900c and N-terminal in the intracellular survival and survival under different stress conditions inside the host.

Biography:

Bandana Kumari is PhD scholar in Department of Biotechnology, Chandigarh, India. She has been working on mycobacterial lipases since last four years under the supervision of Prof Jagdeep Kaur. Her expertise is in Molecular biology, Protein chemistry and animal tissue culture.

Microbial Electrochemical Technology for Food Grade Green Chemicals

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Abstract:

The term microbial fuel cell came into existence to generate energy in the form of electricity using microorganisms. In the present era a new interphase is evolving known as microbial electrochemical technology as a sustainable platform. Multi-functional applications of this technology is being explored by the scientists worldwide to meet the global challenges for eco-friendly environment. Microorganisms play a key role in the system, which are generally selected on the basis on their exoelectrogenic properties. We are proposing an application of microbial electrochemical system to convert the plant biomass (lignocellulosics) into valuable chemicals. Plants synthesize a variety of polymers, which can be used as a raw material for the production of several chemicals (sugars, phenolics, acids etc.). In nature, microorganisms degrade these polymers using their specific enzyme activity to get nutrition. A controlled degradation using specialized/purified enzyme is possible, but the conditions required is difficult to maintain in industrial scenario. However, the proposed technique provides a concept of controlled depolymerization of plant polymers using fungal-bacterial electrochemical system. The system is being developed for the depolymerization of lignin to produce natural antioxidants and vanillin. Thus, proving an economic and ecofriendly system for the conversion of plant biomass into useful food grade products.

Keywords:

Antioxidants; Lignocellulose; Microbial electrochemical cell; Vanilin

Biography:

Dr Rakesh Sharma is currently working as an assistant professor in the Department of Biosciences, Manipal University Jaipur, India. He obtained his B.Sc. in Industrial Microbiology, M.Sc. in Microbiology and has completed his Ph.D. in the field of Microbiology. He is actively working in different aspect of Applied Microbiology, which includes lignocellulose degradation, lignocellulolytic enzymes, plant growth promoting bacteria and microbial fuel cells. He was awarded with the prestigious CSIR SRF and UGC DSK Postdoctoral Fellowship. He is having more than 10 years research experience in the field of applied microbiology and more than 5 years of teaching experience to UG & PG students. He has guided several Bachelor's and Master's dissertations. His research articles appeared in various journals of international repute.

Role of Rv0518, a GDSL lipase of *M. tuberculosis* in cell wall remodeling

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Abstract:

Tuberculosis (TB) remains global health problem and has existed for millennia. The etiological agent responsible for this disease is *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*. One quarter of global TB burden relies on India due to HIV co-infection, the emergence of multi-drug resistant (MDR) and extensively drug-resistant (XDR) strains. *In silico* studies revealed that the hypothetical protein of *M. tuberculosis*, Rv0518 belonged to GDSL family of lipases. To decipher its role, rv0518 gene was cloned in pVV16 shuttle vector and expressed in *M. smegmatis* mc2155 strain. The expression of rv0518 was significantly up-regulated under nutrient stress in *M. tuberculosis* H37Ra and the protein was detected in membrane fraction. The expression of rv0518 led to the colony morphological changes, altered growth kinetics, change in biofilm formation capability, provided resistance to various cell wall stresses like SDS, lysozyme and antibiotics to *M. smegmatis*. Moreover, rv0518 expression enhanced total lipid content, especially trehalose dimycolate content in *M. smegmatis*. Hence, Rv0518 is a cell wall associated GDSL lipase that provided resistance to various intracellular stresses by modulating the cell wall composition of the bacterium.

Biography:

Jashandeep Kaur did her PhD from Department of Biotechnology, Panjab University, Chandigarh, India. She had worked on deciphering the role of lipolytic enzymes in the life-cycle of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* under the supervision of Prof. Jagdeep Kaur. Her expertise is in molecular biology, protein biochemistry and animal tissue culture. Currently, she is working as guest faculty in the Department of Biochemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh, India.

Adventitious shoot induction from leaves of *Moringa oleifera* Lam. and metabolite profiling of its gum exudates

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Abstract:

Plants serve as the largest source of naturally derived medicines attributed to their diverse and rich phytochemical profiles. *Moringa oleifera* Lam. is one such mineral packed, nutrient rich and medicinally important tree species of family Moringaceae. The tree is commonly called as the Miracle Tree due to its potential to serve as remedy for a diverse range of diseases and disorders credited to its vast, diversified and unique combination of numerous phytochemicals. In our study we have optimized micropropagation protocol for induction of adventitious shoots from both micropropagated and in situ leaf explants. Micropropagated leaves were found to show maximum percentage of induction (90%) while that in in situ leaves was found to be even less than 50%. The best response in terms of number of shoots (10-12) was observed when explants were cultured on MS medium supplemented with BAP 0.5 mg/l and the maximum number of roots (8-10) were obtained when the induced shoots having at least two nodes were cultured on MS medium supplemented with IBA 0.5 mg/l. Further, profiling of the metabolites present in the aqueous methanolic fraction of the gum exudates was also carried out using GC-MS/MS after derivatization with MSTFA and pyridine. GC chromatogram indicated the presence of around 24 compounds. Mass spectral analysis led to identification of 5 bioactive compounds including betulinaldehyde, W-amyrin, 2-pentanoic acid, trichothecolone and methyl octadecenoate. These compounds are known to possess significant cytotoxic, antitumor, antimicrobial, apoptotic and antifoaming activities. The presence of bioactive compounds in the gum exudates further paves the way to understand the chemistry of the gum for development of different formulations.

Keywords:

Moringa, micropropagation, bioactive compounds, metabolite profiling

Biography:

Dr. Rohit Jain, Assistant Professor, Department of Biosciences, Manipal University Jaipur having specialization in the field of plant tissue culture and experimental morphogenesis and plant metabolomics. He has published more than 15 papers in peer reviewed journals with a combined cite score of 250. He completed his Ph.D. from University of Rajasthan and has teaching and research experience of 8 years. He is the life member of Indian Botanical Society also.

Genome-wide identification and characterization of powdery mildew stress responsive NBS-LRR genes in *Vitis vinifera*

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Abstract:

Fungal diseases such as powdery mildew severely affect the productivity of Viticulture, therefore it is imperative to find genes or resistance loci that imparts tolerance/resistance towards such diseases. Nucleotide binding site leucine rich repeats (NBS-LRR) constitute one of the largest family of R genes that protects plant from pathogenic attack. In the present study, we identified NBS-LRR genes genome-wide during PM infection in grapevine. Consequently, we identified 18, 23, 16, 10, 10, 12, 9, 20 and 14 differentially expressed PM-responsive NBS-LRR genes in seven partially PM-resistant (DVIT3351.27, Karadzhandal, Khalchili, Hussein, O34-16, Late Vavilov and Sochal) and two PM-susceptible (Thompson seedless and Carignan) *V. vinifera* accessions. Altogether, we found 63 distinct PM-responsive NBS-LRR genes amongst all the varieties examined in our study. Of these, 13 genes were found to be common between PM susceptible and resistant varieties and exhibiting higher expression levels in resistant varieties as compared to susceptible ones. Additionally, we found 36 such genes that were showing differential expression only in resistant varieties. Next, we characterized the identified sequences based on physicochemical properties, chromosomal locations, gene structure and motif analysis, and functional annotation by Gene Ontology (GO) mapping. The chromosomal mapping depicted the clustering of majority of genes over chromosomes 12, 13, 14, 15 and 19. Most of the genes identified were intron less or comprised of one intron only and are localized to secretory pathways. For our sequences, the major domains identified were Rx-CC, NB-ARC and LRR. Further, we studied the evolutionary relationships amongst the PM-responsive NBS-LRR genes by performing phylogenetic analysis. Additionally, to determine the regulatory role of NBS-LRR genes against PM stress, various hormone and stress responsive elements were predicted. In conclusion, PM-responsive NBS-LRR genes could possibly be used for improving disease resistance/tolerance in grapes against fungal pathogens.

Biography:

Neetu Goyal is a PhD scholar in Department of Biotechnology, Panjab University, Chandigarh, India. She has been working on the research topic “Identification of Nucleotide Binding Site Leucine Rich Repeats (NBS-LRR) genes associated with fungal resistance in *Vitis vinifera*” since August 2014 till date under the supervision of Dr. Kashmir Singh. Her expertise is in Molecular biology, Plant tissue culture, and bioinformatics.

Polymorphism in CatSper1 Gene in Crossbred (*Holstein Friesian x Deshi*) Cattle in Bangladesh

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Abstract:

Bangladesh Government is promoting sustainable improvements in milk, meat and eggs production. Artificial insemination (AI) with semen from high yielding animals is using to increase milk production. The widespread use of AI has revealed great variation in fertility. The success of AI significantly depends on quality of semen. Assessment of male fertility is traditionally based on microscopic evaluation of semen. However, some of the priced males have a low fertility even when classical semen parameters (i.e. viability, motility, abnormal forms, etc.) are normal. Many genes are known to control sperm motility, among them Cation channel of sperm (CatSper) family mutations resulted in male infertility. This study was therefore, undertaken to identify the polymorphism of CatSper1 gene in crossbred cattle. A total of 54 blood samples were randomly collected from crossbred cattle (*Holstein Friesian x Deshi*) from Sirajganj district of Bangladesh. Nucleotide variation in CatSper1 gene at position 434 and 482 encompassing exon 2, 3 and 4 was evaluated using PCR-RFLP. DNA was extracted from blood samples followed by PCR with targeted primer and restriction analysis with EcoRI, HindIII (exon 2) and PvuII, RsaI (exon 3 and 4). Each of the enzymes cuts the PCR product and generated (315bp, 119bp), (360bp, 74bp) and (403 and 79 bp) (229, 152 and 103 bp) bands respectively against the restriction enzymes. Findings of this study indicate that CatSper1 gene in examined crossbred cattle has no polymorphism in selected position with respect to restriction enzymes used and show the conservedness in these exons in the studied samples.

Keywords:

CatSper1 gene, Crossbred cattle, Polymorphism, Semen

A new knockdown resistance (kdr) mutation F1534L in *Aedes aegypti* is associated with insecticide resistance

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Abstract:

The control of *Aedes aegypti* borne-infections mainly dengue, chikungunya, yellow fever and Zika virus relies mainly on vector control measures in the absence of specific drugs or vaccines available. Emergence of insecticide resistance in *Ae. aegypti* may pose serious threat to the success of insecticide-based vector control programme. Here, we report the presence of multiple knockdown resistance (kdr) mutations present in an Indian *Ae. aegypti* population including a new mutation F1534L (not reported earlier in *Ae. aegypti*) which is associated with DDT and pyrethroid resistance. DNA sequencing of partial domain II, III and IV of the voltage gated sodium channel (VGSC) performed on *Ae. aegypti* collected from Bengaluru, India, revealed the presence of four kdr mutations, i.e., V1016G and S989P in domain II and two alternative kdr mutations F1534C and F1534L in domain III. Allele specific PCR assays (ASPCR) were developed for the detection of kdr mutations V1016G and S989P while a PCR-RFLP based strategy was adopted for the genotyping of F1534L, F1534C and T1520I mutations in domain III. Genotyping of 572 *Ae. aegypti* samples collected in 2014 and 2015 revealed a moderate frequency of V1016G/S989P (18.27%) and F1534L (17.48%), a relatively high frequency of F1534C (50.61%) and absence of T1520I in the population. Mutations V1016G and S989P were in complete linkage disequilibrium while they were having negative linkage disequilibrium with kdr alleles F1534C and F1534L. The new mutation F1534L showed significant protection against permethrin, deltamethrin and DDT whereas F1534C showed protection against permethrin and DDT but not against deltamethrin.